

The Study on the Antifungal Activities of Novel Derivatives of Indole, Benzofuran and Dihydropyrimidine against *Candida*, *Aspergillus* and Dermatophytes Species by Broth Micro-Dilution Method

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ABSTRACT:

Antifungal drugs are one of the medicines group that have the most increasing use in the past few years in human medicine sciences, especially with the development of AIDS epidemic and immunosuppressed diseases. In this line researchers have concentrated the development of new antifungal drugs that have less toxicity and more effective. The aims of this study are synthesis a few numbers of new derivatives of indole, benzofuran and dihydropyrimidine and all these products were evaluated for in vitro evaluation antifungal activity against various species of *Candida*, *Aspergillus*, and Dermatophyte by Broth Microdilution method. They also were investigated against exophiala dermatitidis, *Pseudallescheria boydii*, *Penicillium marneffeii*, *Cryptococcus neoformans* and several species of bacteria, including *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Enterobacter faecalis*. The obtained results were shown that some of them had outstanding effects. This research have also revealed that among the various synthesised compounds with different Structures, benzofuran derivatives were shown the best antifungal activities, while the indole and dihydropyrimidine analogues had no significant antifungal effect.

Keyword: Indole, benzofuran, dihydropyrimidine, antifungal and antimicrobial activity, broth micro dilution method.

INTRODUCTION

Although in the early twentieth century, epidemics of bacterial were the most important mortality factor, fungal infections were not nearly big factor. In the late 1960s, with the rise of antibiotic treatment, a serious increase in fungal infections have been observed. First fungal invade to tissue has been reported in the early years of 1800, and numerous reports of fungal diseases, pathogens, geographic spread of the disease are available after 1900[1]. In recent decades, along with increasing of infectious diseases and weakening of the immune system such as AIDS, cancer, Aging, Diabetes, Cystic fibrosis, new methods of treatment, such as organ transplantation were developed. Moreover, the growth use of immunosuppressive drugs for treatment of autoimmune diseases and increase in chemical therapy against a variety of tumors are occurred. Despite of extensive research and huge studies to control infectious causes, antifungal agents have been remained as a major medical problem [2-5]. Contrary to the development of antifungal drugs in recent years, the number and range of effective treatments are limited and toxicity and pharmacokinetic issues are confronted with some problems that require new compounds to prevent or delay the spread of fungal agents.

Opportunistic pathogenic fungi are divided into yeasts and filamentous fungi categories. Yeasts are large number of unicellular fungi that usually Proliferate by budding. Yeasts in favorable condition and immunocompromised host can create wide range of superficial – mucosal, Systemic, and even fatal disease in susceptible people. Among the pathogenic yeast, *Candida* genus, especially *Candida albicans*, are known as an

opportunistic mucosal pathogen, and the fourth cause of bloody infections (fungemia), and also the most common cause of nosocomial fungal infections [2]. Other *Candida* species, especially *Candida dubliniensis*, in immunocompromised patients (such as AIDS, cancer and transplant patients) may cause systemic fatal infection [3].

Dermatophytes are a group of filamentous fungi that cause dermal fungal infections (Dermatophytosis). The high prevalence of these diseases are entitled in Iran, particularly in Fars province due to the background factors such as hot weather and occupational factors. In the recent years, infections caused by these fungi, especially in people who have immune deficient, are increasing. This causes to an atypical and Progressive lesions. Conventional antifungal therapies do not respond as well to the disease which change to chronic forms [6]. Up to the recent years in our country, Griseofulvin was used for the clinical forms of Dermatophytosis treatment; But because of many side effects of this drug including headache, vomiting, dizziness, it deals to some limits in its use. Also the prolonged use of this drug and the inability to completely eradicate fungal agents (this drug is growth inhibitor) has some limitations, too. In some species of Dermatophyte, the resistance to this drug was observed, thus loss of recovery and repeated episodes of disease was seen [7].

Another group of filamentous fungi is *Aspergillus* which is the major cause of fungal food spoilage and systemic mycoses in immunocompromised individuals [3]. *Aspergillus* Prevalence rate reached its highest level in the last two decades and has become one of the lethal opportunistic invasive fungal infection [8-9].

In previous studies, a number of imidazole drugs, benzimidazole and triazole derivatives were synthesized in Medicinal Chemistry College of Pharmacy, Shiraz Medical Sciences University. And it has been investigated in terms of antimicrobial effects in which some of them were suitable [10-11]. Various studies have shown that some indole derivatives have antimicrobial effects. In the present study, some of these derivatives demonstrated inhibitory effects at 1/0-2/0 mg/ml against *Aspergillus*, *Candida* and *Penicillium* species [12-13]. In another study, nine indole derivatives were evaluated in vitro examination against phytopathogens fungi and most of these compounds were found to possess efficient antifungal activities [14]. Some of the indole derivatives inhibit the differentiation and maturation of bacterial spores' coats and it is effective on the control of gram-positive bacteria [15]. The antimicrobial effects of some dihydropyrimidine and benzofuran derivatives were shown in several studies [16-18]. In a study conducted by Jiang et al. Significant antimicrobial effects by benzofuran derivatives on *E. coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, and *Candida albicans* was observed [19]. In the present study some new benzofuran derivatives demonstrated Antimicrobial activity at 0/1-0/5 mg/ml [20].

In this present study the effect of nine antifungal compounds was investigated on the growth of standard species of *Candida*, *Aspergillus* and Dermatophyte, and it also was investigated against *Exophiala dermatitidis*, *Pseudallescheria boydii*, *Penicillium marneffei*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, and several species of bacteria, including *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Enterobacter faecalis*. At the end of this study the minimum inhibitory concentration and the minimum Fungicidal Concentrations of the effective compounds were determined, in the case of having low cell toxicity, they can be alternative replace to solve the problem of resistance to common antifungal drugs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Compounds

Scheme 1. Chemical reaction for synthesis of new derivatives of indole, benzofuran and dihydropyrimidine

In this study, nine synthesized compounds were determined as antifungal effects compared to conventional antifungal drugs. These compounds have been synthesized through the one pot three component reaction of various 1,3 di carbonyl compounds (3), substituted benzaldehydes (2) and 2-naphthole (1) or aniline

derivatives (4) in the presence of catalytic amount of formic or acetic acid in ethanol as solvent and reflux conditions for around three hours.

The progress of reactions were monitored by TLC. After completion of the reactions the precipitates were collected and recrystallized in EtOH to afford pure products. The structures of products were fully confirmed by instrumental analysis and spectroscopic data.

Microorganisms

Initially, five different synthetic molecules (1A-5A) were studied in terms of inhibitory and fetal effects against seven standard strains of fungi including *Candida albicans* ATCC 10261, *C. tropicalis* ATCC 750, *C. glabrata* ATCC 90030, *C. dubliniensis* CBS8501, *C. krusei* ATCC6258, *Aspergillus flavus* ATCC 64025, *A. fumigatus* ATCC 14110. In addition, the antibacterial activity of the synthesized compounds were studied against standard bacteria including *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923 and *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, which all of them were taken from the reference collections of the ATCC America and CBS Holland companies [21-22].

Then four new substituted of the most effective molecule was synthesized (B-C) and the minimum inhibitory and lethal concentration of these compound was studied on standard strains and also susceptible and azole-resistant clinical isolates with using Broth microdilution method. The standard strain of yeast is containing *Candida albicans* ATCC 10261, 2730, 5982, 1912, *C. glabrata* ATCC 863, 2175, 2192, 6144, 90030, *C. tropicalis* ATCC 750, *C. dubliniensis* CBS 8501, ATCC 7987, 7988, 9788, *C. krusei* ATCC6258. Also *Exophiala dermatitidis* ATCC 120431, *Cryptococcus neoformans* H99 were examined. The standard Filamentous fungi including three strains of *Aspergillus* containing *A. fumigatus* ATCC 14110, *A. flavus* ATCC 64025, *A. clavatus* CBS 514.65, and also *Pseudallescheria boydii* ATCC 329.93, *Penicillium marneffei*. Moreover, the inhibitory activities of the mentioned compounds against Dermatophytes (*Microsporum Canis*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* and *Trichophyton verrocosum*) which were identified by morphological and physiological tests were also examined. At least three species of bacteria, including *S. aureus* ATCC 25923, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, *En. Faecalis* ATCC 11700 were determined as well as six clinical isolates of azole-resistant yeasts identified by PCR-RFLP containing *Candida albicans* SUCC 2033, 625, 203, 634, *C. tropicalis* SUCC611, *C. parapselosis* 194 which all of them were resistant to fluconazole and itraconazole (MIC > 256) and the inhibitory effect of these drugs does not appear on them [23, 24]. The susceptibility of the examined isolates of fungi against fluconazole (for *Aspergillus* species and yeasts) or griseofulvin (for dermatophytes) were examined by broth microdilution method (rezai12). The interpretative breakpoints for susceptibility testing of fluconazole as recommended by clinical and laboratory standards institute (CLSI) were: Susceptible ≤ 8 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, Susceptible Dose Dependent 16-32 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and Resistant ≥ 64 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ [6].

Determination of minimum inhibitory and fungicidal concentrations

Minimal inhibitory concentrations of the synthesized agents and selected drugs against standard and clinical species of the fungi were determined by broth microdilution method as recommended by CLSI, with some modifications [25]. Briefly, the RPMI-1640 (with l-glutamine and phenol red, without bicarbonate) (Sigma,

USA) was prepared and buffered at pH 7.0 with 0.165 mol 3-(N-morpholino) propane sulfonic acid (MOPS) (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany). Serial dilutions of the selected compound (0.5-256.0 µg/mL) were prepared in 96-well microtitre trays using RPMI-1640 media (Sigma, St. Louis, USA) buffered with MOPS (Sigma, St. Louis, USA). Double dilutions of fluconazole were also prepared for each of the tested azol resistance strain of *Candida* with the final concentration of 0.25-128 µg/mL. Stock inoculums were prepared by suspending three colonies of the examined yeasts in 5 ml of sterile 0.85% NaCl, and adjusting the turbidity of the inoculums to 0.5 McFarland standard at 530 nm wavelength (this yields stock suspension of $1-5 \times 10^6$ cells/ml). For moulds (*Aspergillus* spp. and dermatophytes), conidia were recovered from the 7-day old cultures grown on potato dextrose agar by a wetting loop with Tween 20. The collected conidia were transferred in sterile saline and their turbidity was adjusted to OD=0.09-0.11 that yields $0.4-5 \times 10^6$ conidia/ml. Working suspension was prepared by making a 1/50 and 1/1000 dilution with RPMI of the stock suspension for moulds and yeasts, respectively. After addition of 0.1 ml of the inoculums to the wells, the trays were incubated at 30°C for 24-48 h in a humid atmosphere. 200 µl of the uninoculated medium was included as a sterility control (blank).

In addition, growth controls [medium with inoculums and 5% (v/v) DMSO (maximum DMSO concentration) but without the synthetic compounds] were also included. The growth in each well was compared with that of the growth control well. MICs were visually determined and defined as the lowest concentration of the compounds that produced ≥ 50 growth inhibitions. Each experiment was performed in triplicate. MFCs were of the lowest

concentration that showed either no growth or fewer than 4 colonies, which corresponded to 98% killing activity of the initial inoculums. MFCs were also determined by culturing 10 µl from the wells showing no visible growth onto Sabouraud dextrose agar plates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Antibacterial and Antifungal activity

Researches have shown that drugs with indole containing ring, show high biological activity against different bacteria, fungi and viruses. Also indole increased the effective activity of drug [26]. Many natural benzofuran have interesting cytotoxic and Pharmaceutical potential. Several synthetic compounds with this ring structures are associated with various biological activities such as antifungal, antibacterial, antiviral and antitumor. Among the heterocyclic compounds family, nitrogen containing heterocyclic are the most important categories of Medicinal Chemistry. Pyrimidines are an Inseparable part of DNA and RNA, which are demonstrated as one of the most active compounds in this group with a wide range of in vitro biological activities. According to studies, between the heterocyclic, indole and dihydroxy Pyrimidine have shown the highest activity [17]. Some Pyrimidine analogs are discussed as an antimicrobial and antifungal agents with high action potential [27]. In the course of our search for useful therapeutically antifungal agents, we synthesized some new derivatives of indole, benzofuran and dihydropyrimidine (scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Name and Chemical structure of new derivatives of indole, benzofuran and dihydropyrimidine that synthesized for biological tests

Between initial compounds which are synthesized (1A-5A), none of the compounds except 4A has antimicrobial effect on investigated microorganisms at 0.5-256 µg/ml. As shown in Table (1), compounds 4A has fifty percent inhibitory effects on the growth of tested standard species of *Candida* at the concentration of 16-128 and ninety percent growth inhibition at Table 1. The minimum inhibitory and fetal concentration of five initial synthetic molecules on seven standard yeast and mold fungal and two gram-negative and gram-positive bacterial species (µg/mL)

32-256 µg/ml. Also we saw the killing effect against tested yeasts at 64-256 µg/ml. This compound had not any effect against *Aspergillus* genus and bacteria, *S. aureus* and *E. coli* (Table 1).

Compound																			
		MIC	MIC9	MF	MIC5	MIC9	MFC	MI	MI	MF	MI	MI	MF	MI	MI	MFC			
Yeast (number of strains)	<i>Candida albicans</i> ATCC 10261	>25 6	>256 6	>25 6	>256 6	>256 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	16	32	64	>25 6	>25 6	>256				
	<i>Candida dubliniensis</i>	>25 6	>256 6	>25 6	>256 6	>256 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	32	128	256	>25 6	>25 6	>256				
	<i>Candida glabrata</i>	>25 6	>256 6	>25 6	>256 6	>256 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	32	64	64	>25 6	>25 6	>256				
	<i>C.tropicalis</i> ATCC 750	>25 6	>256 6	>25 6	>256 6	>256 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	64	128	128	>25 6	>25 6	>256				
	<i>Candida krusei</i> ATCC6258	>25 6	>256 6	>25 6	>256 6	>256 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	128	256	256	>25 6	>25 6	>256				
Filamentous	<i>Aspergillus fumigates</i>	>25 6	>256 6	>25 6	>256 6	>256 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>256				
	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	>25 6	>256 6	>25 6	>256 6	>256 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>256				
Bacteria(number of		MIC	MIC9	MF	MIC5	MIC9	MFC	MI	MI	MF	MI	MI	MF	MI	MI	MFC			
Gram positive and	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	>25 6	>256 6	>25 6	>256 6	>256 6	>256 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>256				
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	>25 6	>256 6	>25 6	>256 6	>256 6	>256 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>25 6	>256				

Continuing, regarding to compound **4A** had antifungal effects on tested fungi, new derivatives of it (**B-C**) was synthesized. Antifungal effects of new synthetic compounds against filamentous fungi are shown in Table (2) and against yeast fungal are shown in Table (3). Three **B**, **D** and **E** derivate had limited effects against tested fungi and bacteria. But the **C** compound had the most antifungal effects on the standard strains of Dermatophytes. It had fifty percent inhibitory effects on the growth of them at 4-16 µg/ml and ninety percent growth inhibition at 16-64 µg/ml. This compound also resulted killing effect on tested Dermatophytes at 32-256 µg/ml. It had the fifty percent growth inhibition on standard strains of *Candida* at 8-256 µg/ml and ninety percent growth inhibition at 16-256 µg/ml too. Significant antifungal effects on azole resistant yeast strains were observed too and it had Fifty percent growth inhibition at 32-128 µg/ml on, and ninety percent growth inhibition at 128-256 µg/ml. Compared with other yeasts, this compound showed fifty percent inhibitory effect on *Exophiala dermatitidis* at 16 µg/ml and Ninety percent inhibitory effect at 32 µg/ml. Also it killed this strain at 128 µg/ml.

These drugs effect on the filamentous fungi, *Aspergillus* species, *Pseudallescheria boydii*, *Penicillium marneffeii* and microbial standard strains under study was not observed.

Table 2. The minimum inhibitory and fetal concentration of four secondary synthetic molecules on fungal standard species of mold and bacteria (µg/mL)

DISCUSSION

Among the initial synthesized substances, two compounds which known as following structures: 5-(2-(4-nitrophenyl)naphtho[2,1-b]furan-1-yl) pyrimidine-2,4,6-(1*H*,3*H*,5*H*)-trione (**1A**), and 2-(5-chloro-3-(4-nitrophenyl)-1*H*-indol-2-yl)cyclohexane-1,3-dione (**4A**), are from Naphthofurane derivatives, which are only the compound **4A** with contains of phenyl ring in C-2 position of benzofurane and also cyclohexene-1,3-dione in C-3 position of this ring with two methyl group substrate in the concentration range of 0.5-256 µg/ml have antifungal and antibacterial effect on tested microorganisms. The antifungal effect investigation of initial compounds on yeasts and standard microbial and mold fungal are given in table (1). compound **4A** had 50% growth inhibitory effect on standard strain of *Candida* yeasts at 16-128 µg/ml, besides, had 90% growth inhibitory effect at 32-256 µg/ml. additionally, we have been considered the fetal effects on tested yeasts at 64-256 µg/ml. In contrast, this compound had no effect on strand strain of *Aspergillus*, and bacterial species containing *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. Localizing of nitro-group on C-4 phenyl ring and substitution of pyrimidine ring instead of cyclohexene-1,3-dione on **1A** compound, revealed to antifungal declension properties.

Compound														
Fungi (number of strains)		MIC5 0	MIC9 0	MFC	MIC5 0	MIC9 0	MFC	MIC5 0	MIC9 0	MFC	MIC5 0	MIC9 0	MFC	
filamentous	<i>Aspergillus fumigates</i> ATCC	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	
	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> ATCC 64025	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	
	<i>Aspergillus clavatus</i>	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	
	<i>pseudallescheria boydii</i>	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	
	<i>Penicillium marneffeii</i>	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	
	<i>Microsporium canis</i>	>256	>256	>256	16	64	256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
	<i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i>	>256	>256	>256	16	64	256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Trichophyton verrucosum</i>	>256	>256	>256	4	16	32	8	64	64	>256	>256	>256	>256	
Bacteria(number of strains)		MIC5 0	MIC9 0	MFC	MIC5 0	MIC9 0	MFC	MIC5 0	MIC9 0	MFC	MIC5 0	MIC9 0	MFC	
Gram	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	
	<i>Enterobacter</i>	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	

One of the reasons shall be depend on electronegative effect of nitro group on phenyl ring and varying in polarization of molecule.

The compounds of: 2-(5-chloro-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1H-indol-2-yl)-5,5-dimethylcyclohexane-1,3-dione (**2A**) and 2-(5-chloro-3-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-indol-2-yl)cyclohexane-1,3-dione (**3A**), are from indole derivatives. According to various extend efficiency of compounds, reported in literatures, we had expected that the **2A** and **3A** structures had an appropriate effect as antifungal and antimicrobial efficiency. However no salient effects have been shown of these compounds on discussed strains. This effect have explanation as following reason that, the substitution of several chemical groups in indole substances resulted decreasing or increasing in molecular spatial and charge distribution, conjunction to target molecule proportion and also causes antifungal and antimicrobial effects. The presence of *p*-chlorophenyl in C-3 position on indole ring in **2A** compound in comparison of *p*-nitrophenyl group in the same structure at mentioned position in **3A** compound had contemporary effect, however the presence of two methyl group in cyclohexene-1,3-dione ring in **2A** compound, couldn't improve the antifungal and antimicrobial properties. Compound 5-(3-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-nitro-1H-indol-2-yl) pyrimidine 2,4,6-(1H,3H,5H)-trione (**5A**) is from dihydropyrimidine derivatives with indole ring. According to investigations in hetrocycles, indoles and dihydropyrimidine

had the most activities between these structures [20]. It seems that more of dihydropyrimidine derivatives had antifungal activities in comparison of antibacterial effects. Besides, neither antifungal nor antibacterial effects exhibited from compound **5A**. In contrast of our imagination which expected to show considerable effects in the mentioned compound by presence of dihydropyrimidine and indole ring, simultaneously, the presence of nitro group in C-5 position on indole ring revealed to disappear the biological effect of the compound. In addition this structure had no consider effects, like (**2A**) compound, that might be the presence of chloro and nitro group in the structure in C-5 position of indole ring have similar effect on deactivation of molecule. As reported literatures about pyrimidines activations board, which are C-4, and C-5 of these molecules, and since existing of various groups in this positions, the biological effects are more undertaken of these groups. It is be notable that in **5A** structure the C-5 position of pyrimidine ring occupied by indole substrate, and it seems that the most sterically inhibit exhibited for the molecule to annihilate the biological effects. As a result an appropriated compound between these initial classify compounds in this study, is **4A** compound growth inhibitory effect on candidate standard strain. This compound had no effect on strand strain of *Aspergillus*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. In the next stage, different derivatives from the presence compound was synthesized and examined from the

antifungal and antibacterial properties approach. The antifungal activities of novel synthesized compounds in relation of strain fungal, was shown in table (1-2) and the next, in relation of yeast fungal was observed in table (3).

Table 3. The minimum inhibitory and fetal concentration of four secondary synthetic molecules on standard yeast species and azole resistant strains ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)

Compound												
	MIC5	MIC9	MF	MIC5	MIC9	MF	MIC5	MIC9	MF	MIC5	MIC9	MF
YEAST												
<i>Candida albicans</i>	>256	>256	>256	32	128	256	256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Candida albicans</i>	>256	>256	>256	256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Candida albicans</i>	>256	>256	>256	64	256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Candida albicans</i>	>256	>256	>256	128	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Candida dubliniensis</i>	>256	>256	>256	16	64	>256	128	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Candida dubliniensis</i>	>256	>256	>256	8	16	256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Candida dubliniensis</i>	>256	>256	>256	16	64	128	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Candida dubliniensis</i>	>256	>256	>256	128	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Candida glabrata</i>	>256	>256	>256	64	256	>256	128	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Candida glabrata</i>	>256	>256	>256	64	256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Candida glabrata</i>	>256	>256	>256	256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Candida glabrata</i>	>256	>256	>256	64	256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Candida glabrata</i>	>256	>256	>256	64	256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>C. tropicalis</i> ATCC 750	>256	>256	>256	128	256	256	128	>256	>256	64	128	256
<i>Candida krusei</i> ATCC 6258	>256	>256	>256	8	32	256	128	>256	>256	64	>256	>256
<i>Candida albicans</i> *	>256	>256	>256	128	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Candida albicans</i> *	>256	>256	>256	128	>256	256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>C. tropicalis</i> *	>256	>256	>256	64	256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Candida albicans</i> *	>256	>256	>256	32	128	256	128	256	256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Candida parapsilosis</i> *	>256	>256	>256	64	128	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Candida albicans</i> *	>256	>256	>256	128	256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i>	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256
<i>Exophiala dermatitidis</i>	>256	>256	>256	16	32	128	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256	>256

*Azol resistance

In the compound of 5,5-dimethyl-2-(2-(4-nitrophenyl)naphtho[2,1-b]furan-1-yl)cyclohexane-1,3-dione (B), by addition of nitro group in C-4 of phenyl ring in relation of (4A) compound, we had released the antifungal and antimicrobial effects. In the compound, 2-(2-(4-chlorophenyl)naphtho[2,1-b]furan-1-yl)-5,5-dimethylcyclohexane-1,3-dione (C), by addition of chloro group

in C-4 of phenyl ring in relation of (4A) compound, considerable effects was observed on standard strain Dermatophytes, and At 4-16 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, resulted 50% growth inhibitory, besides, had 90% growth inhibitory effect at 16-64 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. This compound also, was annihilated treated Dermatophytes in the range of 32-256 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. the mentioned compound had considerable effects on

studied yeasts in relation to another synthesized derivatives and at 8-256 µg/ml, resulted 50% growth inhibitory on candidate standard strain, Moreover, had 90% growth inhibitory effect at 16-256 µg/ml. In some substances hadn't observed 90% growth inhibitory effect. The results are comparable with **4A** compound. The above compound was annihilated some strain yeast (*Candida albicans*, *C. tropicalis*, *C. dubliniensis*, *C. krusei*). The killing effects on some strains in ratio **4A** compound demonstrated decreasing statement.

In some of the azole resistance strain of yeasts, observed a substantial antifungal effects. Compound C resulted 50% growth inhibitory, at 32- 128 µg/ml, and 90% growth inhibitory effect at 128-256 µg/ml.

In comparison of candidate yeasts, Compound C obtained 50% growth inhibitory at 16 µg/ml, and 90% growth inhibitory effect at 32 µg/ml for *Exophiala dermatitidis*. Furthermore, decomposition of this fungal at 128 µg/ml, attended to this phenomena, we never seen any effect on mold fungi containing *Aspergillus*, *Pseudallescheria boydii*, *Penicillium marneffeii*, and standard microbial species.

In compound: 2-(2-(4-chlorophenyl)naphtho[2,1-*b*] furan-1-yl)cyclohexene-1,3-dione (**D**), by elimination of dimethyl from cyclohexene-1,3-dione ring, in relation of compound **C**, the biological effects have been decreased potentially, and we had established only 50% growth inhibitory at 8 µg/ml, and also 90% growth inhibitory effect at 64 µg/ml for *Trichophyton* species. However we haven't considered the fetal effects on treated Dermatophytes at 64 µg/ml. besides, 50% growth inhibitory effect observed on candida standard strain at 128-256 µg/ml. In addition compound: 6-hydroxy-2-(2-(4-nitrophenyl)naphtho[2,1-*b*]furan-1-yl)pyrimidine-2,4(*1H,3H*)-dione (**E**) have not showed antifungal and antibacterial effects, like **B** compound. We have monitored only 50% growth inhibitory effect on two yeast species (*Candida tropicalis*, *C. krusei*) at 64 µg/ml. It means that, occupation of C-3 position on indole ring with dihydropyrimidine substrate, instead of cyclohexene-1,3-dione couldn't be optimize and stimulate biological efficiency.

CONCLUSION

The observation of structural associations and efficiency of these substances demonstrates that, **4A** and **C** compounds had an excellent effect on most investigated strain fungal, except strand fungal and microbial strains, which are evident in some cases growth inhibitory effect and another case fetal effects of aforementioned molecules. In addition in comparison of Fluconazole and Itraconazole, these substances showed an appropriate effect on azole resistance strains. These structures have both the same substrate cyclohexene-1,3-dione in C-3 position of naphthofurane ring, and the variance of them is presence of chloro group on *p*-position of phenyl ring conjugated to naphthofurane moiety which had not considerable effect on results, so since of more identical structure conformation, carried out contemporary efficiency, approximately. Moreover compound **C** indicated growth inhibitory and fetal effects on Dermatophytes fungal. So, in relation of common antidermatophytes drugs, like Griseofulvin, which are growth inhibitor of these fungal have priority efficiency.

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